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**A new subspecies of *Purpuricenus interscapillatus* Plavilstshikov, 1937
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from Cyprus**

M.A. Lazarev¹, R. Ambrus²

¹Free Economic Society of Russia, Department of Scientifics Conferences and All-Russian Projects

Tverskaya str., 22a, Moscow 125009 Russia

e-mail: cerambycidae@bk.ru, humanityspace@gmail.com

²Tmukovo nám. 1112/1, CZ-152 00 Prague 5, Czech Republic

e-mail: ambrus@centrum.cz

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Abstract: *Purpuricenus interscapillatus cypriensis* **ssp. n.** close to *P. i. nudicollis* Demelt, 1968 is described from Cyprus. *Purpuricenus cornifrons* Sabbadini & Pesarini, 1992 recently published as a species (Danilevsky, 2020) is downgraded to subspecies rank: *P. interscapillatus cornifrons* Sabbadini & Pesarini, 1992, **stat. rest.**

Introduction

The name *Purpuricenus interscapillatus* Plavilstshikov, 1937 was proposed instead of *P. budensis* var. *humeralis* Pic, 1891 - not *P. humeralis* (Fabricius, 1798) from North America. According to Rapuzzi & Sama (2014) the species consists of 8 subspecies: *P. i. interscapillatus* Plavilstshikov, 1937 (South Turkey from Taurus Mts to Mardin, though the authors also recorded “the nominative subspecies from Lebanese mountains”), *P. i. longevittatus* Pic, 1941 (Liban), *P. i. barbarae* Rapuzzi & Sama, 2014 (Israel), *P. i. hermonensis* Rapuzzi & Sama, 2014 (Israel, Syria); *P. i. nabateus* Sama, 1999 (Jordan); *P. i. nudicollis* Demelt, 1968 (South Turkey, Antalya and Cyprus); *P. i. cornifrons* Sabbadini & Pesarini, 1992 (East Turkey between Tunceli and Mus); *P. i. sasanus* Kadlec, 2006 (Iran, Lorestan). Danilevsky (2020) upgraded two names to species rank: *P. cornifrons* Sabbadini & Pesarini, 1992 and *P. sasanus* Kadlec, 2006. *P. interscapillatus marivanensis* Danilevsky & Faizi, 2020 from Iran (Kurdistan) was described as new.

A new subspecies very close to *P. i. nudicollis* Demelt, 1968 is described below from Cyprus.

Materials and methods

Specimens were photographed under a microscope AmScope SM745NTP with an attached Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1-30.5 mm 1:2.8-4.5. The illustrations were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20.

Types material studied are deposited in the following collections:

MD - collection of M. Danilevsky (Moscow, Russia)

ML – collection of M. Lazarev (Moscow, Russia)

RA – collection of R. Ambrus (Prague, Czech Republic)

SM – collection of S. Murzin (Moscow, Russia)

Results

Purpuricenus interscapillatus cypriensis ssp. n.

Figs 1-2

Type locality. Cyprus, Pafos, Pano Panagia environs.

Description. Head with very short genae, about 4 times shorter than lower eye lobes, frons transverse with very dense conjugating small punctation; vertex with sparser punctation; labial and maxillary palpi very short, slightly elongated; antennal tubercles short, obliterated; distance between upper eye lobes about as wide as scapus; antennae relatively short, reaching elytral apex in males by 8th -9th joints, antennae in females a little longer or a little shorter than body; 3rd antennal joint is the longest, 4th joint about equal to 5th and longer than 1st.

Prothorax transverse, in males about 1.3 times wider (at middle) than long, in females - 1.25-1.3 times wider than long, about 1.3 times wider posteriorly than anteriorly; lateral side evenly curved, with very small tubercle, often totally obliterated; pronotum strongly convex, with very dense regular punctation, with very small smooth spot behind middle; central part of pronotum glabrous, lateral - with scattered setae; red pronotum bordered anteriorly with very narrow black edge, posteriorly - with wider black stripe protruding anteriorly with elongated oblique appendages; scutellum black,

triangular.

Elytra relatively narrow, parallelsided, in males and in females 2.0-2.2 times wider (at base) than long; red elytral portions glabrous anteriorly, but with very fine short recumbent pubescence posteriorly, as well as on black portions; black elytral design elongated, slightly convex at middle, never protruding anteriorly close to scutellum, widened along hind elytral margin; elytral apices truncated, usually slightly convex at middle with small, but distinct outer and inner angles; body length in males: 12.9-15.2 mm, width (at humeri): 3.8-4.7 mm; body length in females: 11.7-15.9 mm, width (at humeri): 3.6-5.0 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The new taxon is very close to *P. interscapillatus nudicollis* (with glabrous lateral pronotal margin), but all specimens with numerous fine erect setae on lateral pronotal surface.

Materials. Holotype, male, Cyprus, Pafos, Pano Panagia env., wine trap, 18.6.2004, M. Novotný leg. - ML; 12 paratypes; 3 males, 4 females with same labels - ML, RA; 1 female, Pafos, Miliou env., 265 m 17.6.2015, R. Ambrus leg. - ML; 1 female, Pafos distr., 19-27.5.2014, piège aerienn: vin, G. Miessen leg. - SM; 1 male, 2 females, Limassol, Alassa env., 350 m, wine trap, 13.6.2015, R. Ambrus leg - ML, RA.

Materials used for comparison. *P. interscapillatus interscapillatus*: 1 female, Turkey, Erdemli - Aslanli, 8.-12.6.2002, R. Ambrus leg. - RA; 1 male & 1 female, Turkey, 15 km NW Erdemli, 36°41'38.51"N, 34°9'44.85"E, 24.6.2008, R. Ambrus leg. - RA; 1 male, Turkey, Çamliyayla env., 37°10'7.24"N, 34°36'14.75"E, 21.6.2008, R. Ambrus leg. - RA; 1 female, Turkey, Karadut env., 45 km NEE Adiyaman, 37°55'6.46"N, 38°48'39.73"E, 16.6.2008, R. Ambrus leg. - RA; 1 female, S.O. Anatolien, nach Ersin b. Dörtüol, 20-22.6.1937 Ramme leg. - RA; 1 male, Turkey, Belen env., 36°29'38.01"N, 36°12'57.44"E, 20.6.2008, R. Ambrus leg. - RA; 1 male, 2 females, Turkey, Belen, 16-17.6.1991, A. Kudrna leg. - RA; 1 male, Syria, Al Haffe E of Lattakia 430 m, 20.6.2008, T. Tichý leg. - RA.

P. interscapillatus nudicollis: 1 male, Turkey, Alanya, Akseki, 1100 m, 10-19.6.2001, O.& J. Gregory leg. - RA; 1 female, Turkey, 14 km NE Alanya, Dim Valley, 29.6.2006 R. Ambrus leg. -

M.A. Lazarev, R. Ambrus

RA; 1 female, Turkey, Antalya env., Karaman, 6.1973, K. Bernhauer leg. - RA; 1 male, Turkey, Antalya, 8.6.1975, K. Bernhauer - MD.

Fig. 1-2. *Purpuricenus interscapillatus cypriensis* ssp. n.:
1 - Holotype, male, Cyprus, Pafos, Pano Panagia env., wine trap, 18.6.2004, M. Novotný leg.; 2 – Paratype, female, Pafos, Miliou env., 265 m 17.6.2015, R. Ambrus leg.

M.A. Lazarev, R. Ambrus

Purpuricen *interscapillatus cornifrons* Sabbadini & Pesarini, 1992,
stat. rest.

Purpuricen *cornifrons* Sabbadini & Pesarini, 1992: 58, 62 - "Regione del lago di Van"; Danilevsky, 2020: 280 - Turkey.

Purpuricen (*Purpuricen*) *cornifrons*, Sama & Löbl, 2010: 198 - Turkey; Sama, Rapuzzi & Özdikmen, 2012: 30 - Turkey; Bingöl, Muş.

Purpuricen *interscapillatus cornifrons*, Rapuzzi & Sama, 2014: 151 - Eastern Turkey: mountains between Tunceli and Mus.

The subspecies status of the name introduced by Rapuzzi & Sama (2013) was rejected by Danilevsky (2020) without any arguments and original status *P. cornifrons* was returned. So, I prefer to restore a subspecies rank *P. i. cornifrons* Sabbadini & Pesarini, 1992, **stat. rest.**

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M.A. Lazarev, R. Ambrus

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